

we will present several other issues including ones for which we have not yet found solutions. We believe that a wider discussion with other projects in this session will be beneficial to all.

7 RE-WORKING OF THE NUMISMATIC DATABASE OF THE NIETULISKO MAŁE HOARD APPLYING INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS AND RTI DOCUMENTATION

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Databases are a solid foundation for modern numismatic research, widely used nowadays. During a recent project which applied big data methods and cloud processing to the digitalization and dissemination ca. 2,800 coins from the hoard from Nietulisko Małe, Ostrowiec County technical investigation need to focus not only providing new imagery and migrating the old databases but also on re-working the database to be created in accordance to international standards and FAIR principles.

The database was done with a view to adapting it to modern standards. It is one of the largest deposits discovered in Poland, which has not been properly published yet. For this work, that will be the basis for future research in numismatics, it was important to implement RTI (Reflectance Transformation Imaging) documentation for these coins - one of the best methods of coin archiving. It would facilitate numismatic research, especially with coins that are illegible or in a bad state of preservation.

RTI needs around 30 images, means that the final documentation will be the taking of over 180,000 images with different light positions. It was decided to build a solution using big data and cloud computing. This raises the question of archiving and sharing this type of data in accordance with FAIR, but is this justified when no one will probably ever be interested in it? The very use and sharing of RTI technology also raises some questions - it is relatively easy to share and display this type of imagery in a local database, but how to share this type of data within Linked Open Data - if there is no clear FAIR-compliant standard for its storage, and even less so for its display. The aim of the presentation is to answer the above questions.

8 LEGACY COINS: MAKING ROMAN COINS OF THE PAST COMPATIBLE WITH THE FUTURE

Welte, Micheline (Austrian Archaeological Institute) - Burkhart, Karl (Austrian Archaeological Institute) - Schwaiger, Helmut (Austrian Archaeological Institute)

For many years, the Austrian Archaeological Institute (OeAI) hosted an online Roman coin database known as dF-MRÖ; however, the database was not being realised to its full potential and a decision was made to update it in order to more closely adhere to modern data standards. Thus, OeAI.COIN was envisioned – a database to host the OeAI legacy coin collection in a modernized and interoperable format with Linked Open Data, which would allow for the standardized import of future coin collections, while adhering to the FAIR Principles of data management and employing links to specialist authority databases and ontologies, such as NOMISMA.

In the process of the coin database's transformation into OeAI.COIN, a variety of issues cropped up that involved difficulties in adapting the previous dataset to more modern standards. There was a lack of standardization of the data, low quality photos, redundant information, as well as ambiguous and non-standardized vocabulary to name just a few. In addition, the potential to include 3D data was not available. The OeAI will discuss its attempt at preparing its archaeological legacy collections for the future.

9 CHANGES IN HUMAN-PLANT INTERACTIONS IN CENTRAL ITALY OVER TIME: COLLECTION AND COMPARISON OF PUBLISHED AND UNPUBLISHED ARCHAEOBOTANICAL DATA

Moricca, Claudia (Department of Environmental Biology, Sapienza University of Rome) - Florenzano, Assunta (Department of Life Sciences, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia) - Mercuri, Anna (Department of Life Sciences, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia) - Sadori, Laura (Department of Environmental Biology, Sapienza University of Rome)

Recent advancements in the field of archaeobotany have significantly enhanced our understanding of the historical interactions between humans and plants in Italy. This includes insights into ancient diets, resource selection, introduction of allochthonous economic plants, and their ceremonial applications. Despite the diffusion of archaeobotanical research, accessing this information remains challenging due to its dispersion across various scientific papers and archaeological reports, with the latter being particularly difficult to obtain. Moreover, this data is typically restricted to isolated findings or specific sites, which complicates the assembly of a comprehensive historical perspective.

The establishment of the Botanical Record of Archaeobotany Italian Network (BRAIN) in 2015 marks a significant stride towards consolidating information about historical human-plant relations across Italy. This collaborative network and database compiles an extensive inventory of archaeological sites, detailing their specific locations, chronological context, culture, and the array of archaeobotanical research carried out, complete with bibliographic citations. This database is regularly enriched with the latest scholarly contributions.

Within the scope of the PNRR PE5 CHANGES Spoke 8 and CN5 NBFC Spoke 3 projects, this study introduces a georeferenced instrument designed to synthesize and compare data on plant macro-remains from archaeological and historical sites. This tool collates findings from both published sources within BRAIN and unpublished studies, standardizing the information and categorizing it chronologically. Currently focusing on central Italy, the initiative is set to expand and encompass the entire nation. By employing this newly formulated dataset, the process of reconstructing past dietary patterns and tracking the introduction of new species from the Neolithic period to the present becomes more feasible and direct. Consequently, this will enhance our ability to trace traditional plant uses in the past, including trade and importation showing origins and proliferation of archaeophytes and neophytes throughout the Italian Peninsula.

10 **TRANSPARENT INTEGRATION AND REUSE OF LARGE ARCHAEOLOGICAL DATASETS: A CASE STUDY FROM NEOLITHIC AND BRONZE AGE SOUTHERN SCANDINAVIA**

Bilotti, Giacomo (Kiel University)

The exponential growth of data accessibility presents archaeologists with an unprecedented resource. The amount of open databases and datasets, ranging from simple spreadsheets to complex architectural assemblages, significantly expands the horizons of archaeological research. However, numerous archaeological sites from commercial archaeology excavations are continuously flowing into regional and national databases. Despite their potential, these datasets often remain underutilised in scholarly research due to challenges related to data homogeneity and reusability.

This paper explores the potential and issues of this vast source of data for archaeologists, especially in terms of modelling. Here, I use Neolithic and Bronze Age societies in southern Sweden and Denmark as a case study, showing how diverse and large-scale datasets can be effectively combined, tackling common issues such as data uncertainty and the need for homogenisation. I argue for the necessity of a straightforward and transparent methodology to effectively integrate legacy data into our models (e.g. consistent use of regular expressions), enabling straightforward adaptation or replication by the academic community as new data emerges or old projects conclude.

The approach presented here is fully documented and accessible in a dedicated GitLab repository, written using R, a well-known and open-source programming language and software environment for statistical computing. While acknowledging the limitations inherent in these data sources, the paper also proposes potential solutions for their effective use and integration into archaeological research.

11 **VISUALIZING ARCHAEOLOGICAL DATA - SMALL PROJECTS, BIG PROBLEMS**

Molander, Paula (Rio Kulturlandskapet; Gothenburg University)

Utilizing digital tools for the visualization of archaeological information, notably through web-based interactive maps, is an effective strategy for engaging with the general public as well as professionals in the archaeological field. However, what challenges might arise when developing interactive web maps intended for public consumption?

Archaeological data can be labour-intensive to effectively manage and present visually. The process of extracting and compiling data, in large volumes, is often complicated, with the available data being highly diverse and often originating from a variety of sources. Furthermore, ensuring accessibility for the general public puts different demands on the format of visualization than if only created for professionals.

This paper discusses two instances where the objective was to present archaeological data to a general audience using interactive web maps. Open-source tools such as QGIS and Leaflet were employed in both cases, ensuring method reusability. The goal is to identify common challenges encountered by professionals when creating visual formats for large volumes of varied data, regardless of project size or ambitions, and to discuss potential opportunities and solutions for these issues.

12 **IMPLEMENTING DATA MANAGEMENT STRATEGY BASED ON AGILE SCRUM METHODOLOGY WITHIN THE AL-ULA CULTURAL PROJECT (UCOP)**

Leschallier de Lisle, Anne (ARCHAIOS) - Gourret, Gaël (ARCHAIOS) - Charbonnier, Julien (ARCHAIOS) - Kanhoush, Yasmin (ARCHAIOS; ARCHEORIENT UMR 5133)

Within the framework of the Al-Ula Cultural Oasis Project (UCOP) – carried out by Archaios, funded and steered by the French Agency for AIUla Development on behalf of the Royal Commission for AIUla – a large-scale comprehensive survey of over 4000 hectares of gardens has been conducted between 2019 and 2023, resulting in the